

Comparative study of *Eugenia jambolana* (Jamun) and *Alium Cepa* Linn. (Onion bulb) as hypoglycemic and hypolipidemic agent in Diabetes mellitus type II

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ABSTRACT:

In the current study, 60 obese and diabetic subjects between the ages of 35 and 55 were examined to determine the hypoglycemic and hypolipidemic effects of *Eugenia jambolana* Jamun pods and *Alium Cepa* Linn. (Onion bulb) powder. Both serum lipids and serum glucose were measured for each individual. The current study's findings suggest that the use of herbs is safe and beneficial in the early stages of type 2 diabetes, with Jamun being the best hypoglycemic agent when compared to *Alium Cepa* Linn. (Onion bulb).

Keyword: Diabetes melitus type II, *Alium sativum*, *Eugenia jambolana* Jamun, medicinal plants.

1. INTRODUCTION:

Diabetes mellitus, also known as "Madhumeha," has been well-known for centuries and has turned into a global disease. A disruption of glucose homeostasis characterizes this chronic metabolic disease. Diabetes is a chronic, untreatable illness that affects practically all of the body's organs and systems. Several plants have proven helpful for people with diabetes. The seed contains a glucoside jambolline ellagic acid, yellow essential oil, chlorophyll, resin, gallic acid and albumin etc. The bark has around 20% gum. It acts as an astringent and is used to cure skin disorder. The bark powder is sprinkled in bleeding disorder and wounds. Fruit pulp mixed with sesame oil is applied in burning sensations on the skin. Its fruit is an appetizer, digestive and liver stimulant. Impairment of liver function associated with diabetes is improved by seed powder. It is also an astringent. Leaves have anti-emetic property while bark is astringent. Excessive use of the fruit may cause constipation. The fruit and fruit juices are effective in disorders like loss of appetite, indigestion, pain and dysentery. its ethanolic extract shows hypoglycemic activities in albino rabbits. Later French scientists **Sigogneau- Jagodzin-ski et al.1967**, proved that constituents isolated from ethanolic extract had hypoglycemic action on alloxan induced diabetic rats (**Sigogneau-Jagodzinski et al;1967**). **Ratsimamanga et al.1972**, has reported ethanolic extract of bark of jamun tree has been used to decrease blood glucose level by 21% after one hour in hyperglycemic rabbits in a dose corresponding to 10g/ kg dry bark (**Ratsimamanga et al.1972**). According to (**R. Bansal et al; 1981**) oral feeding of seeds at 170, 240 and 510 mg/rat for 15 days, maximum reduction in blood glucose of normal fasted rats was observed at 240 mg/rat doses in comparison to chlorpropamide treatment. In addition, there was a 2.4-6.8-fold and 9.2-fold increase in cathepsin B activity pertaining to proteolytic

conversion of proinsulin to insulin by seed extracts of *E. jambolana* and chlorpropamide respectively in rats (**Bansal et al; 1981**).

. In folk medicine, onion has been used for asthma, bronchitis, whooping cough, and similar ailments. (**Blumenthal M. et al 1999**), Fresh onion bulbs are used at daily doses of 50 g; dried onion is used at a dose of 20 g/day for dyspepsia. Contraindications have not yet been identified. (**Ensminger et al; 1994, Dwyer I et al; 1986. Blumenthal sr. ed et al; 1998 and Fleming et al; 1998**), Observed that the onion plant is a perennial herb growing to about 1.2 m, with 4 to 6 hollow, cylindrical leaves. On top of the long stalk, greenish-white flowers are present in the form of solitary umbels growing up to 2.5 cm wide. (**Schulz V et al: 1998**) Onion skin dye has been used for egg and cloth coloring for many years in the Middle East and Europe.

A Meta analysis of selected clinical trials employing garlic preparation showed significant reduction of total serum cholesterol, in human subjects *Eugenia jambolana (Jamun)* purportedly lowers circulating triglycerides. It is one of those herbs which have favorable effect as hypoglycemic and hypolipidemic agent. The main aim of this study was to see the effect of Garlic pods as hypoglycemic and hypolipidemic in Diabetes melitus type 2.

2. MATERIAL AND METHOD:

2.1 Experiment Place:

This study was conducted in Dept. of Biochemistry M.G.M. Medical College and Associated M.Y. Hospital Indore. And the subjects were selected from the outpatient Department of Medicine M Y Hospital Indore

2.2 Plant Collection:

All the plant components are bought from Ayurvedic shop Indore.

2.3 Inclusion Criteria:

Selection of subjects was done on basis of Blood Glucose not more than 180 mg/dl and HBA1C not more than 8mg%

2.4 Exclusion criteria:

History of any other clinical complication, taking any drug therapy Pregnant and lactating ladies.

Subjects were informed about the study in detail and consent was also taken before study.

2.5 Ethics Committee: The Ethics Committee of MGM Medical College approved the study.

2.6 Normal Healthy Control (n=50):

2.7 Study Subjects (n=200):

Estimations of the Biochemical parameters were done on study subjects then were compared with Healthy control.

2.8 Study subjects were divided into groups

i) *Alium Cepa Linn. (Onion bulb) group (n=40) &*

ii) *Eugenia jambolana (Jamun) Group (n=40)*

2.9 Procedure:

A study was done to evaluate the hypoglycemic and hypolipidemic effects of *Eugenia jambolana* (Jamun) pods and *Alium Cepa Linn.* (Onion bulb) powder. Among the 60 obese and diabetic subject of 35 years to 55 years. 10 were taken as healthy control and 25 diabetic and obese were treated with *Eugenia jambolana* (Jamun) pods and 25 were treated with *Alium Cepa Linn.* (Onion bulb) powder. The criteria of inclusion of study group in subjects was FBS > 110 mg/dl of glucose, >290 mg/dl of cholesterol, > 210 mg/dl of triglyceride, then 180 mg/dl of LDL. All the subjects were examined for serum glucose and serum lipids. *Eugenia jambolana* (Jamun) & *Alium Cepa Linn.* (Onion bulb) powder 100mgs/day was given to the subjects of study group for 6 months and sample were collected at the starting day of study after two months, fourth and after six months of study for estimation of all parameters.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Table No. 01 Comparison between *Alium Cepa Linn.* (Onion bulb) and *Eugenia jambolana* (Jamun) supplement groups after a period of two month

PARAMETER	JAMUN Mean 6 SD	Onion Mean 6 SD	t value	p value
FBG mg/dl	122.60±9.10	139.15±11.23	5.11	<0.0001
PPBG mg/dl	176.8±6.53	185.05±11.95	2.70	<0.0001
CHOLESTROL	261.00±55.67	261.80±10.92	0.06	>0.05
TG mg/dl	107.00±3.65	107.20±5.20	0.14	>0.05
HDL mg/dl	37.50±2.94	44.70±2.93	7.73	<0.0001
LDL	63.05±5.30	62.40±4.00	0.43	>0.05
HBA1C mg%	7.70±.23	7.21±.68	3.19	<0.0001
UREA mg/dl	26.39±4.14	23.65±4.33	2.04	<0.01
CREATININE mg/dl	.88±.081	.84±.086	1.48	>0.05
URIC ACID mg/dl	3.76±.39	4.02±.32	2.29	<0.01

Table no 1 after two months- The results are as follows Fasting Blood Glucose, Post Prandial Blood Glucose, Serum HDL, and HbA1c is highly significant. Serum Total Cholesterol, Serum Triglycerides, Serum LDL, Serum Creatinine are non-significant. Serum Urea, Serum Uric Acid is significant (but within normal limits).

Table No.2 Comparison between *Alium Cepa Linn.* (Onion bulb) and *Eugenia jambolana* (Jamun) supplement groups after a period of four month

PARAMETER	JAMUN Mean 6 SD	Onion Mean 6 SD	t value	p value
FBG mg/dl	95.40±9.62	123.90±5.78	11.35	<0.0001

PPBG mg/dl	152.95±14.05	167.15±12.54	-3.37	<0.0001
CHOLESTROL mg/dl	248.50±10.33	245.05±6.69	1.25	>0.05
TG mg/dl	104.20±5.24	108.10±4.86	2.43	<0.0001
HDL mg/dl	37.10±3.75	48.15±2.79	10.55	<0.0001
LDL	58.30±4.55	56.00±2.75	1.93	>0.05
HBA1C	6.21±.41	6.45±.59	1.45	>0.05
UREA mg/dl	23.10±3.72	23.30±5.44	0.13	>0.05
CREATININE mg/dl	.72±.09	.87±.09	5.15	<0.0001
URIC ACID mg/dl	3.88±.38	3.80±.35	0.68	>0.05

Table no 2 after four months- Results observed are as follows Fasting Blood Glucose, Post Prandial Blood Glucose, Serum Triglycerides, Serum HDL are highly significant. Serum Total Cholesterol is non-significant. Serum LDL, HbA1c, Serum Urea, Serum Uric Acid is non-significant. Serum Creatinine is found to be highly significant within the normal limits.

Table No. 3 Comparison between *Alium Cepa Linn.* (Onion bulb and *Eugenia jambolana* (Jamun) supplement groups after a period of six month

PARAMETER	JAMUN Mean 6 SD	Onion Mean 6 SD	t value	p value
FBG mg/dl	77.50±9.09	117.10±6.21	16.07	<0.0001
PPBG mg/dl	140.00±10.21	151.05±4.71	4.39	<0.0001
CHOLESTROL mg/dl	241.85±5.45	233.30±9.40	3.51	<0.0001
TG mg/dl	106.30±4.11	103.45±3.85	2.25	<0.0001
HDL mg/dl	40.25±2.93	52.95±5.083	9.67	<0.0001
LDL	56.10±4.37	53.50±2.98	2.19	<0.0001
HBA1C	4.97±.66	6.07±.29	6.83	<0.0001
UREA mg/dl	20.10±2.84	21.95±4.74	1.49	>0.05
CREATININE mg/dl	.63±.11	.80±.108	4.87	<0.0001
URIC ACID mg/dl	3.82±.45	3.73±.30	.68	>0.05

Table no 3 after six months - Fasting Blood Glucose, Post Prandial Blood Glucose, Serum Total Cholesterol, Serum Triglycerides, Serum HDL, Serum LDL and HbA1c is highly significant. Serum Urea, Serum Uric Acid are non-

significant. Serum Creatinine is found to be highly significant (but within normal limits) after six months of herbal supplements.

4. CONCLUSION:

Results of the current research Conclude that *Eugenia jambolana (Jamun)* is the best hypoglycemic agent in comparison to *Alium Cepa Linn. (Onion bulb)*, and that herbal treatment is safe and efficient in the early stages of Diabetes mellitus type 2. The herb *Eugenia jambolana (Jamun)*, which is a common choice for folk medicine and also has to be taken into consideration as a source for alternative medicine, is highlighted in the current studies as having the best hypoglycemic agent.

5. REFERENCES:

1. Sigogneau-Jagodzinski, M., Bibal –Prot, P., Chanez, M. and Boiteau, P., Hypoglycemic and antidiabetic activity of principle extracted from Eugenia jambolana, C. R. Acad Sci Hebd Seances Acad Sci parries, Ser D., 264 (8), 1967,1119-1123.
2. Rastimamanga, A. R., Lefournier-Contensou, C., Bibal Prot, P., Comparative study of the effect of a principle extracted from Eugenia jambolana bark with N, N-methyl dimethyl biguanide and glibutimine on induced hypoglycemia in normal rats, C. R. Acad Sci Hebd séances Acad Sci D, 275 (8), 1972, 913-915.
3. Bansal, N., Ahmad, N., and Kidwai, J. R., Effects of oral administration of Eugenia jambolana seeds and chloramide on blood glucose level and pancreatin cathepsins B in rat, Indian J. of Biochem and Biophys, 18, 1981, 377.
4. Blumenthal M, Goldberg A, Brinckmann J, eds. Herbal Medicine: Expanded Commission E Monographs. Newton, MA: Integrative Medicine Communications; 1999.
5. Ensminger AH, Ensminger ME, Konlande JE, Robson JR. Foods & Nutrition Encyclopedia. Vol. 2. 2nd ed. Boca Raton, FL: CRC Press Inc.;1994:1684-1688.
6. Dwyer J, Rattray D. Magic and Medicine of Plants. Pleasantville, NY: The Reader's Digest Association, Inc.;1986:261.
7. Blumenthal, M. The Complete Commission E Monographs. Boston: Integrative Medicine Publications; 1998.
8. Fleming T, Second edition. PDR for Herbal Medicines. Montvale, NJ: Medical Economics Company, Inc.; 1998:624-625.
9. Schulz V, Hänssel R, Tyler VE. Rational Phytotherapy: A Physician's Guide to Herbal Medicine. Berlin: Springer-Verlag; 1998;153.